

Appendix_B1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Establishing clear and rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria is essential to ensure the selection of high-quality, relevant studies that contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. In this study, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed to focus on literature that directly addresses spatial teaching practices, barriers, and enablers in primary education.

Inclusion Criteria
Relevance to Spatial Teaching
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Studies that explicitly address spatial teaching, spatial reasoning, or spatial skill development within primary education contexts.• Research examining pedagogical strategies, interventions, or professional development (PD) programs aimed at enhancing spatial ability in young learners.
Focus on Barriers and Enablers
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Studies that identify, analyze, or discuss challenges (barriers) and facilitating factors (enablers) influencing the integration of spatial teaching in classroom settings.
Target Population
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Research focusing on primary school students (typically aged 5–12) and/or primary school teachers involved in spatial instruction.
Publication Type and Quality
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters from reputable publishers.• Empirical studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses that present data, frameworks, or case studies related to the research topic.
Time Frame
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Studies published within the past 10–15 years to ensure the inclusion of recent advancements and current educational practices.
Language
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Publications available in English to ensure accessibility and consistency in interpretation.
Geographical Scope
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Studies conducted in diverse educational contexts, including but not limited to Ireland, Latvia, Sweden, and the Netherlands, to enable cross-cultural comparisons.

Exclusion Criteria
Irrelevant Focus
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies focusing on spatial ability in secondary or tertiary education without connections to primary education. • Research addressing spatial reasoning in non-educational contexts (e.g., medical imaging, architecture, or navigation).
Theoretical or Opinion-Based Works
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinion pieces, editorials, and theoretical papers lacking empirical data or practical applications.
Grey Literature
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissertations, theses, blog posts, and unpublished manuscripts that do not meet peer-reviewed standards.
Language Barriers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications in languages other than English, unless translations or comprehensive abstracts are available.
Time Frame Exclusions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies published before the defined cut-off date to ensure the relevance of contemporary practices.
Population and Setting
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research focusing on populations outside the age range of primary school students, or studies involving spatial skills in professional or adult contexts.

By applying these criteria, the study ensured that the selected literature directly contributed to the development of a pedagogical framework for spatial teaching, while minimizing the risk of irrelevant or outdated findings.